

Interplay of organizational change and trust on the organizational effectiveness in the College of Engineering of the Nueva Vizcaya State University Bambang Campus: Perspective of generation XYZ faculty members

Jeanelyn R. Tominez¹, Jerry F. Tominez², Salvador A. Loria Jr.², Noel T. Florencondia²

¹*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Nueva Vizcaya State University, Bambang Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines*

²*College of Engineering, Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, Nueva Ecija, Philippines*

Corresponding email: tominezjeanelyn@gmail.com ; jerrytominez@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The complex interconnections between organizational change, organizational trust, and organizational effectiveness among the College of Engineering faculty members of the Nueva Vizcaya State University have been investigated. This research employed a descriptive-correlational method, utilizing a structured questionnaire with a four-point Likert scale as the principal data-gathering instrument. The data that have been gathered from the questionnaire are analyzed using statistical tools such as the mean, which is used in determining the respondents' assessment level on organizational change, trust, and effectiveness while the Pearson-r correlation is used to determine the significant relationship between the respondents' perceived level of organizational change, trust, and effectiveness. Findings showed a very high positive correlation between organizational change and organizational trust, as well as between organizational change and effectiveness, and between organizational trust change and effectiveness, based on Pearson r-coefficients of 0.69, 0.62, and 0.54, respectively. Dealing with the level of organizational change in terms of the climate of change and factor analysis of change-specific process factors; level of organizational trust in supervisor, peers, and upper management; and lastly level of organizational effectiveness in terms of goal attainment, efficiency, employee satisfaction and engagement, communication and information flow, human resources, innovation and adaptability and stakeholder satisfaction have an overall high mean of 3.20, 3.19 and 3.09 respectively. In response to these insights, organizational development interventions and training designs were designed to bolster or sustain trust levels during organizational changes and to enhance the rapport between administrators and faculty.

ARTICLE INFO

Received : Jan. 16, 2025

Revised : Feb. 22, 2025

Accepted : Mar. 31, 2025

KEYWORDS

*Organizational change,
Organizational effectiveness,
Organizational trust*

Suggested Citation (APA Style 7th Edition):

Tominez, J.R., Tominez, J.F., Loria, S.A., Jr., & Florencondia, N.T. (2025). Interplay of organizational change and trust on the organizational effectiveness in the College of Engineering of the Nueva Vizcaya State University Bambang Campus: Perspective of generation XYZ faculty members *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management*, 5(1), 82-99.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15192801>

INTRODUCTION

The Nueva Vizcaya State University (NVSU) is one among the 2300 higher education institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines that is known as a very competitive and a premier university not only in the province but throughout the country with its vision to become the leading university in education, innovation, and sustainable development. The university has achieved milestones and prestigious awards in regional, national, and even international as evidenced by the best practices in the international research arena, extension services, and other programs. These achievements are because of trust, effectiveness, and change in the university. Hence, trust, effectiveness, and change are the most essential factors for the success of a higher education institution (HEI), just like NVSU. With these, faculty members can work together toward achieving the university's mission and vision. In the evolving landscape of higher education, the capacity of institutions to adapt to change while maintaining trust and effectiveness is paramount. Organizational change within educational institutions can manifest in various forms, including structural reorganization, policy shifts, technological integration, and curricular reforms. For the Generation XYZ faculty, adapting to these changes involves navigating new systems, aligning with updated practices, and often redefining their roles within the institution. Effective change management is crucial, not only for the successful implementation of new initiatives but also for minimizing disruptions and maintaining morale among faculty.

It is denied that the only thing that is constant in the world is change. Development in today's environment entails letting go of outdated ideas and accepting fresh viewpoints. Academic institutions must also change to fit into a complicated and competitive environment. Any change attempt must have the support of the organization's members to succeed, and organizational leaders who can inspire this support are crucial (Ashkenas et al. 2013). According to Al-Abrow et al. (2019b) and Peng et al. (2020), a reaction is a behavioral and cognitive response to a change that is founded on flexibility and an in-depth grasp of how to respond to a change. This is largely dependent on how supervisors execute changes and how people respond to them.

Typically, resistance to change occurs when it is anticipated to lead to increased workload, uncertainty, and exhaustion, particularly when change is and affects the entire company or significant portions of it (Beare et al., 2020; Li et al., 2017). Individuals' responses to organizational change are anticipated to depend on how they perceive and evaluate how the change will affect them personally. This argues that an individual's attitudes, beliefs, and feelings about a change combine to form their response to the change. How people respond to organizational change will determine whether a change is implemented successfully (Shura et al., 2017). Reactions to a change are directly tied to participation in the change process. When practitioners comprehend the need for change, they are more likely to be able to diagnose patients accurately and increase their readiness to change (Albrecht et al., 2020). Additionally, people are more likely to commit to a change if they believe it will meet their expectations and encounter little resistance to it (Helpap, 2016).

According to some studies, although there is general interest in the organizational change process, the majority of attempts resulted in the process being executed poorly, which ultimately led to failure (Hussain et al., 2018). This is since several secondary variables were prioritized over the main factor of how people and organizations responded to organizational change in those studies (Oreg & Berson, 2011; Alnoor et al., 2021). Less resistance to change might be anticipated as a result of a positive reaction that enables people to be more job-focused. In a similar vein, a negative response to change frequently results in a strong resistance to change. If change is viewed as harmful, this occurs. Additionally, when professional connections are in danger due to a change in circumstances that forces them to quit their jobs, people tend to respond negatively (Michela & Vena, 2012). However, some people react hesitantly to change, especially when the results in the future are uncertain. Reactions are used to deal with and engage with change because this causes disruption and worry for both companies and individuals (Blom, 2018).

These factors imply that depending on individual perspectives, people respond to organizational change in different ways. Organizational routines are disrupted by organizational change, which can undermine trust and lead to risky situations that affect both employee and organizational performance. Therefore, given the relationship's increased

fragility, the creation and maintenance of trust in management is becoming more and more crucial (Bachmann & Inkpen, 2011; Fulmer & Gelfand, 2012; Gustafsson et al., 2021). Organizational change has three components according to Bouckennooghe et al., (2009) which included climate of change, dimensional change, and readiness of dimensional change within an organization. Consequently, the faculty needs to adopt to change in the university to be adept to organizational change.

The literature on knowledge management has emphasized the importance of trust as a component in the success of knowledge management techniques. Particularly, the significance of sharing knowledge and trust has received considerable attention (Ozlati, 2015). Additionally, scholars have been interested in the role that trust plays in protecting knowledge or how to communicate knowledge only with the appropriate parties (Olander et al., 2015). One may argue that trust promotes collaboration and knowledge sharing both within and across enterprises. In the knowledge-based network economy, trust has generally been regarded as a crucial component, particularly because it is thought to operate as a lubricant for handling uncertainty, complexity, and related hazards.

Since trust is crucial in organizational settings and to produce a variety of results, it is a goal for all kinds of businesses to increase employee trust in their employers (Brühl et al., 2018; Fulmer, 2018). Without the support and confidence of internal organizational stakeholders, such as managers and employees, organizations are likely to perform worse and have lower productivity levels (Vanhala & Dietz, 2015). According to some, organizational effectiveness is only achievable when interdependent actors collaborate successfully in an environment of good trust, and as a result, trust affects organizational-level outcomes like innovativeness and performance (Vanhala & Ritala, 2016; Koohang et al., 2017).

Effectiveness, organizational change, and trust are all related. Although change upends patterns and makes workers feel vulnerable, trust promotes one's capacity to manage vulnerability through interpersonal contact, open information sharing, communication, and feedback (Gustafsson et al., 2021; Lewicki & Brinsfield, 2012; Savolainen, 2011; Bachmann & Inkpen, 2011). With a leadership authority mechanism, trust influences behavior, which is reflected in performance. The ability of the organization's members to perform efficiently and productively depends on their ability to have trust in the organization's leadership, their fellow employees, the organization, and its clientele. According to Office of the State Personnel documents from 2015, an effective organization is set up to be able to do things like: (a) adapt quickly to a changing environment; (b) effectively carry out its mission; (c) wisely utilize the knowledge, skills, and abilities of its employees; (d) encourage effective communication and the flow of information necessary for every employee to do a good job; and (e) promote decision-making at the level of the organization that is most appropriate. There are many ways to construct and model an organization, Morgan (2006) stressed, with significant implications for the effectiveness criterion. Every component must be functioning properly for the organization to be productive. For the entire organization to function at its best, each component must fit and collaborate with other components. The components of a company known for excellence are in harmony, making the total more potent than the sum of its parts (Office of the State Personnel, 2015). Before beginning any organizing, managers must decide how the organization will be structured.

An association between management trust and effectiveness measures like work performance and effectiveness has been found in prior empirical research (Li & Tan, 2013; Drescher et al., 2014; Su et al., 2020a, 2020b; Tisu et al., 2021; Hou et al., 2021). Although employee well-being is influenced by trust, the relationship between trust and leadership performance across sectors, which establishes the desired behaviors essential for effectiveness, has received little attention (Gustafsson et al., 2021; Lyu & Chen, 2022; Tisu et al., 2021). Trust has an impact on performance and is a key determinant of organizational effectiveness. (Drescher et al., 2014; Su et al., 2020a,b). Furthermore, trust is likely to boost employees' productivity, organizational effectiveness, and the extent to which they strive toward shared objectives. Previous studies have found a link between effectiveness and proficiency, particularly work-role performance and adaptability. Leadership techniques may boost effectiveness since employees' motivation to invest in their work depends on job clarity, skilled leadership with feedback, and the creation of opportunities (Tisu et al., 2021). In contrast, Yin (2014) investigated the employee situation and organizational change in the intra-organizational context, focusing on how members of the organization construct

and perceive their experiences (Gioia et al., 2012) concerning organizational trust that may have an impact on effectiveness. In a similar line, it may be claimed that trust inside an organization promotes knowledge sharing, which in turn impacts the members of the company's overall effectiveness. Companies need to establish a culture of information sharing and organizational trust if they are to succeed in continuously delivering wholly new or better products and services (Ansari & Malik, 2017). Within-organization trust is crucial in creating this type of culture (Vanhalala & Ritala, 2016). Recent research has looked closely at how cooperation, empowerment, and participation can lead to employee involvement, which is crucial for supporting organizational change (Bah et al., 2024)

Even though many researchers have worked to conduct several studies to try and analyze the nature of cognitive and behavioural responses, such as job satisfaction, individual performance, emotional intelligence, readiness for organizational creativity, organizational management, organizational culture, and other organizational researches, few studies have examined how employees react to organizational change, how their trust in one another affects the functioning of the organization, and how these factors interact. As a result, there have been more studies that investigated how people react to change, but it is still unclear how to assign the many study case types to the most important factors that affect how people react to change, whether they do so positively or negatively, and how well an organization function effectively. Therefore, more research is required about organizational change, organizational trust, and organizational effectiveness. This methodical analysis aims to offer practical insights into settings of change reactions and help the authors identify existing approaches and research gaps in this field. This study thus satisfies the identified literary demand.

The pattern of equilibrium between organizational trust (Scott, 1981) and organizational transformation (Bouckennooghe et al., 2009) is not well documented empirically. Furthermore, little empirical research distinguishes between these two variables, and nothing in the body of literature has looked at how organizational change, organizational trust, and organizational effectiveness interact in different contexts. As a result, linking organizational change and organizational trust that results in increased organizational effectiveness becomes essential to the future work environment of the organization's members. The organization at NVSU continues to strive for excellence to offer its clients, which includes teachers and all other staff members involved in providing high-quality education and exceptional services. The researcher has noticed that change is a constant at the institution. The researcher also noted the importance of trust today, which might ultimately have an impact on the effectiveness of the members of the organization, particularly given that the university's faculty in the College of Engineering is made up of a variety of generations, which can lead to discrepancies. The university's academic members represent a variety of cultures, philosophies, and generations. Further, this study was conducted to measure the present status of the faculty on their organizational trust, effectiveness, and chance for benchmarking purposes, which can be a basis in implementing programs in the university that can help enhance the faculty's organizational trust and effectiveness as they embrace change. This study can also benefit the baby boomers who can learn from this study as they work in the university.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aimed to determine the interplay of organizational change and trust on the organizational effectiveness of the faculty members in the College of Engineering at Nueva Vizcaya State University for the school year 2022-2023.

Specifically, it aims to attain the following research objectives:

1. To identify the respondents' level of assessment on organizational change in terms of the climate of change and factor analysis of change-specific process factors;
2. To identify the respondents' level of assessment on organizational trust along with trust in supervisor, trust in peers, trust in upper management, and organizational trust;
3. To identify the respondents' level of assessment of organizational effectiveness in terms of goal attainment, efficiency, employee satisfaction and engagement, communication and information flow, human resources, innovation and adaptability, and stakeholder satisfaction;

4. To unveil if the respondents' level of assessment on organizational change and organizational trust significantly relate to and
5. To unveil if the respondents' assessment of organizational change and trust with their organizational effectiveness significantly relate.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Quantitative research was used to assess the effectiveness of the organization, change in the organization, and organizational trust among the faculty members in the College of Engineering of Nueva Vizcaya State University (NVSU). This research quantifies respondents' attributes to provide a systematic analytical framework and involves meticulously interpreting and statistically analyzing raw numerical data to generalize conclusions. Quantitative research, like Bhandari's (2020), comprises the systematic collection and analysis of numerical data and the detection of patterns, development of hypotheses, causality examination, and extrapolation of results to larger populations. In addition, this study employed the descriptive-correlational method, utilizing a structured questionnaire as the principal data-gathering instrument. The selection of this method is based on the intent to describe specific phenomena and collect information with analytical interpretation. Utilizing a quantitative research design employing a descriptive-correlational method is of paramount importance when investigating the intricacies of organizational effectiveness, its correlation with organizational change, and perceived organizational trust. This methodological approach ensures an objective measurement of variables pertinent to the study, enabling the researcher to quantify different facets of these constructs with precision and accuracy, thus minimizing bias and subjective interpretation. Furthermore, the descriptive aspect of quantitative research allows for the identification of patterns and trends within the data, providing valuable insights into the current state of organizational dynamics. Through correlational analysis, the researcher was able to delve deeper into the relationships between these variables, shedding light on the interplay between organizational effectiveness, change initiatives, and trust dynamics among faculty members. Importantly, the generalizability of quantitative findings allows for broader implications beyond the confines of the university, offering insights applicable to similar educational institutions and organizational settings.

Meanwhile, the evidence-based approach facilitates informed decision-making by administrators and policymakers, guiding strategic interventions aimed at enhancing organizational effectiveness, managing change, and fostering trust within the university community. Moreover, quantitative research enables the formulation and testing of hypotheses, providing predictive insights into future trends and outcomes, thus contributing to the advancement of organizational development initiatives. Hence, employing a quantitative research design employing a descriptive-correlational method provides a strong framework for unraveling the complexities of organizational dynamics and informing strategic decision-making processes within NVSU and beyond.

Survey Questionnaires

The primary tool used for data collection in this research was a survey questionnaire, which consisted of three separate parts. The first portion of the study was centered on evaluating the effectiveness of the organization. The second component was tailored to evaluate the process of organizational change. Lastly, the objective of the third component was to assess the level of organizational trust inside the organization. Twenty (20) respondents from the College of Engineering were given a questionnaire since this is the only total number of available faculty members workforce. They are instructed to indicate their views by selecting the choices that most accurately align with their ideas and experiences. The focus of the questionnaire is on organizational change and trust. The questionnaire on organizational change was utilized to measure respondents' perceptions, which was adapted from The Organizational Change Questionnaire–Climate of Change, Factor Analyses of Change developed by Bouckennooghe et al. (2009). This instrument encompasses two key dimensions: climate of change and factor analyses of change. A Cronbach's value of 0.81 indicates good internal consistency, affirming the reliability of measuring these dimensions. Respondents were asked to provide their responses to each item using a four-point Likert scale, allowing for nuanced assessments of their perceptions regarding organizational change. The four-point Likert scale is chosen over five-point or seven-point Likert scales because it excludes a neutral option, forcing respondents to pick a side. This can

result in more definitive input since it decreases the chance of "fence-sitting," in which respondents choose a neutral option without fully meditating on their position. This method is particularly appropriate when a clear attitude, such as market research or customer satisfaction surveys, is needed. Moreover, the respondent's uncertainty and misunderstanding are decreased by the smaller number of response possibilities. Quicker responses and maybe higher survey completion rates can result from a simpler scale because respondents can more easily express their ideas without having to navigate multiple-choice questions. This scale facilitates the quantification of respondents' attitudes and perceptions, enabling researchers to gather detailed insights into the organizational change processes within the study's setting. The instrument is scaled, and respondents were offered four options to select from:

Rating	Qualitative descriptions
4	Always
3	Often
2	Sometimes
1	Not all

To arrive at a verbal description of each item, the following arbitrary numerical guide was used:

Range	Qualitative descriptions
3.25 – 4.00	Very high
2.50 – 3.24	High
1.75 – 2.49	Average
1.00 – 1.74	Low

Conversely, the faculty's organizational trust was assessed using the organizational trust questionnaire. This was adapted from Scott's (1981) creation of four organizational metrics of trust: organizational trust, peer trust, superior trust, and top management trust. A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.85 indicates good internal consistency, affirming the scale's reliability in measuring these dimensions. A four (4) Likert Scale was used for the responses to all items. This instrument was scaled, and the respondents were offered four (4) choices similar to the Likert scale used in organizational change.

Lastly, the organizational effectiveness questionnaire was adopted from Vadil and Castriciones (2022) which includes dimension 1- goal attainment; dimension 2-efficiency; dimension 3- employee satisfaction and engagement; dimension 4- strategic clarity; dimension 5- communication and information flow; dimension 6- human resource; dimension 7- innovation and adaptability; and dimension 8- stakeholder satisfaction. A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.89 indicates good internal consistency, affirming the scale's reliability in measuring these dimensions. A four (4) Likert Scale was used for the responses to all items. This instrument was scaled, and the respondents were offered four (4) choices to select from:

Rating	Qualitative descriptions
4	Strongly agree
3	Agree
2	Disagree
1	Strongly disagree

Statistical Treatment

After the data was gathered through the questionnaires, statistical tools such as the mean, which is used in determining the respondents' assessment level on organizational change, organizational trust, and organizational effectiveness, were performed. Other than that, the Pearson-r correlation is used to determine the significant relationship between the respondents' perceived level of organizational change, organizational trust, and organizational effectiveness, which is given by the equation

$$r = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

where:

r is the Pearson correlation coefficient

x_i is the x variable in a sample

\bar{x} is the mean values of the x variable

y_i is the y variable in a sample

\bar{y} is the mean values of the y variable

The determination of the relationships between the variables was made and the interpretation is shown below.

Computed r -values	Qualitative descriptions
1.0	Perfect correlation
0.71 – 0.99	High correlation
0.41 – 0.70	Marked correlation
0.21 – 0.40	Low or slight correlation
0.00 – 0.20	Negligible correlation

All statistical inferences were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Assessment on Organizational Change in Terms of the Climate of Change and Factor Analyses of Change-Specific Process Factors

The findings for the respondents’ level of assessment on organizational change in terms of the climate of change and factor analyses of change-specific process factors as shown in Table 1 consistently exhibit a "high" level of assessment regarding organizational change, evidenced by the computed overall mean of 3.20. Specifically, regarding the climate of change and factor of analyses of change dimensions, their assessment remains steadfastly "high," with a grand mean of 3.21 and 3.19 respectively.

Table 1. Mean and Qualitative Description of the Respondents’ Assessment of Their Organizational Change in the College of Engineering

Organizational change components	Mean and Qualitative Description			
	Generation X	Generation Y	Generation Z	Overall Mean
Climate of Change	3.18 (High)	3.12 (High)	3.12 (High)	3.21 (High)
Factor analyses of change	3.24 (High)	3.01 (High)	3.33 (High)	3.19 (High)
Overall mean	3.21 (High)	3.06 (High)	3.33 (High)	3.20 (High)

Here, the climate change dimension data reveals a consensus among faculty respondents across different generations, all of whom assessed this dimension as "high." However, there are slight variations in mean scores observed among the generations: Generation X reported a mean of 3.18, Generation Y recorded a mean of 3.12 while Generation Z incurred the highest overall mean of 3.21. It is possible to read the above data to suggest that all three of the XYZ generations are flexible and adapting to change, but that Generation Z employees are more resilient and adaptive due to their more flexible and adaptive work styles. They can handle uncertainty, swiftly adapt to new circumstances, and flourish in fast-paced professional settings. Their adaptability and willingness to evolve may support organizations in navigating global upheavals and maintaining their competitive edge. They are fast to

embrace change and swiftly adjust to new circumstances, technology, and work dynamics. This skill is very helpful in today's rapidly evolving workplace. Macpherson (2017) supports these results by pointing out that certain individuals within the firm can adapt to change, which is especially important given the 75% to 88% change failure rate.

On the other hand, the factor analyses of change-specific processes reveal a striking consensus among respondents, who collectively rated this dimension of organizational change as "high," as evidenced by the computed area mean of 2.97. Remarkably, this sentiment transcends generational boundaries, with faculty respondents from all three generations consistently evaluating this dimension as "high." Notably, variations in mean scores are observable across generations: Generation X reported a mean of 3.24, Generation Y recorded a mean of 3.01, and Generation Z exhibited the highest mean score of 3.33. The three generations of XYZ agreed on factor analyses of change-specific processes, and the aforementioned findings may be further construed to suggest that the goal of the organizational change was to direct the decision-making processes in both situations. The purpose of the management change was to improve performance in both public and private organization cases by making clearer the responsibilities of employees in the former instance and collaborating units in the latter. Members of organizations should be aware of the changing environment they are in throughout transitions. The foundation of an organization's climate is what keeps its internal members together throughout tough times and may guide managing the challenges associated with changes (Bouckennooghe et al., 2009; cited in Whitaker, 2020).

The empirically proven, interconnected roles that climate of change and change-specific process elements play in promoting effective outcomes account for the high overall mean in organizational transformation or change research. Studies repeatedly demonstrate that a positive change atmosphere, which is defined by clear communication, leadership support, and shared beliefs of adaptability, fosters alignment and lowers resistance. Additionally, transformational leadership has a direct impact on mission, strategy, and culture (Errida et al. 2021). According to factor analyses such as structural equation modeling and confirmatory factory analysis, organizational resources like leadership and climate and job resources like role clarity and training associated with change constitute higher-order factors that account for 73–81% of the variation in engagement measures (Albrecht et al., 2022; Appelbaum et al., 2017). Because organizational environment and systems (such as adaptive policies and feedback mechanisms) function indirectly through job resources to increase commitment rather than directly, these resources mediate engagement. This provides strong support for these elements' constant importance in research by confirming their coherence and reliability (Bouckennooghe et al., 2009).

Level of Assessment on Organizational Trust Along with Trust in Supervisor, Trust in Peers, Trust in Upper Management, and Organizational Trust

Based on the information shown in Table 2, it can be deduced that the respondents had a "high" level of evaluation about the trust that they have in their organizations. This is demonstrated by the grand mean score of 3.19. To be more precise, they continue to rank supervisors’ trust as "very high," with a mean score of 3.54. But trust in superior management, which has a mean score of 3.03, and trust in peers, which has a mean score of 3.33, were both evaluated as "high." In addition, the overall mean of the trustworthiness of the organization is 2.87.

Table 2. Mean and Qualitative Description of the Respondents’ Assessment of Their Organizational Trust in the College of Engineering

Organizational trust components	Mean and Qualitative Description			
	Generation X	Generation Y	Generation Z	Overall Mean
Trust in supervisor	3.67 (Very High)	3.62 (Very High)	3.33 (Very High)	3.54 (Very High)
Trust in peers	3.38 (Very High)	3.45 (Very High)	3.17 (High)	3.33 (Very High)
Trust in upper management	3.00 (High)	2.93 (High)	3.17 (High)	3.03 (High)

Organizational trust	3.08 (High)	2.70 (High)	2.83 (High)	2.87 (High)
Overall mean	3.28 (Very High)	3.18 (High)	3.13 (High)	3.19 (High)

In terms of supervisor’s trust, results reveal that the respondents gave this dimension an overall rating of "very high," yielding an impressive area mean of 3.54. Particularly, the data shows that faculty respondents from generation XYZ had "very high" rates with area means of 3.67, 3.62, and 3.33, respectively. The outcome indicates that the respondents do have trust in their supervisors, especially those from generations XYZ. However, the result is evident in that a supervisor's and employee's trust creates a great work environment where people feel empowered and driven to succeed, which raises their self-esteem and increases output. In every context, higher levels of trust are predicted to result in better work, more collaboration, and more favorable attitudes. Higher levels of trust between people create a climate at work that is more favorable for cooperation to occur naturally. Consequently, this leads to increased self-assurance and improved performance, which fosters a more optimistic attitude among the team. Mutual respect and good communication are based on trust, which is the cornerstone that eventually drives success. Vanhala and Dietz (2015) provided evidence to support the claim that reliable relationships—particularly the trust that employees have in their supervisor—are a strong predictor of client satisfaction. Furthermore, the welfare of employees is impacted by supervisor trust. The link between trust and management performance across professions, which forms the essential behaviors for effectiveness, has received less attention.

Dealing with trust in peers, the respondents gave this factor an overall rating of "very high," resulting in an outstanding area mean of 3.33. Interestingly, the data shows that faculty respondents from various generations generally agreed that this dimension was "very high" in generations X and Y with area means of 3.38 and 3.45. while an area mean of 3.17 in generation Z with a qualitative description of “high”. The results presented above indicate that the Generation XYZ have a high level of trust in their colleagues in the company. It is generally accepted that in a variety of work environments, higher levels of trust promote improved performance, more collaboration, and more positive attitudes. In the end, this positive feedback loop helps people as well as improving the quality of services clients get. Establishing and fostering trust creates a more pleasant and productive work atmosphere where providing excellent service becomes a goal in and of itself. Building stronger working connections is essential to ensuring that organizations successfully accomplish their objectives. This is where trust comes in. Rahayuningsih's (2019) research on the benefits of organizational trust found that it may both raise retention intentions and lessen the probability of employees to leave the organization. Furthermore, Hunt et al.'s (2009) research found a clear correlation between an organization's level of trust and its success or failure. Although building and sustaining trust within an organization is very difficult and demands continuous oversight, the advantages of doing so are widely shared.

Going to the next dimension, which is the trust in upper management, findings showed that a grand area mean of 3.03 was reported by the respondents from the three Generations, indicating a "high" degree of trust in their upper management. The generations' mean scores did, however, differ slightly from one another. Generation Z had the highest mean score, 3.17, followed by Generation X (3.00) and Generation Y (2.93). Employee evaluations from different generations indicate that the upper management of the organization is adequately trustworthy. Trust is crucial to leadership because it fosters positive connections, boosts team morale, and makes communication easier. It also enables leaders to more effectively motivate and lead their staff. The research by Vanhala and Dietz (2015), which claims that without the assistance and confidence of organizational internal stakeholders, such as employees and senior management, organizations are likely to have impaired performance and lower productivity levels, supports this.

Lastly, results showed a “high” level of organizational trust among the respondents with an area mean of 2.87, a slight difference in the rating of the three Generations with 3.08 as the highest mean coming from Generation X, followed by 2.83 mean of Generation Z and 2.70 from Generation Y. The result indicated above demonstrates the extent to which the respondents had trust in their organization. Within an organization, trust cannot be purchased or commanded; it must be earned. Upholding organizational trust is essential since it will ultimately decide whether a company, corporation, or educational institution succeeds or fails. The research conducted by Hunt et al. (2009) indicates a clear correlation between an organization's level of trust and its success or failure. Although building and

sustaining trust within an organization is very difficult and demands continuous oversight, the advantages of doing so are widely shared.

Trust in peers, supervisors, senior management, and organizational trust all have high overall means, which is indicative of their interdependent and empirically supported functions in promoting employee engagement and productivity. Research shows that trust in school officials and supervisors is directly increased by transformational leadership (e.g., encouraging adaptation and a common goal), which in turn affects job satisfaction and lowers inclinations to leave (Nazmul Islam et al., 2020). For example, confidence in management accounts for up to 81% of the variation in job resources (autonomy, role clarity, etc.), which in turn influences employee engagement (Gopalan et al., 2023). Another illustration is the genuine leadership among Spanish employees that raised emotional commitment by 30–40% by influencing distributive justice views, with trust serving as a mediating factor (González-Cánovas et al., 2024). Factor analyses show that these trust dimensions generate higher-order constructs: job resources (like peer cooperation) and organizational resources (like climate and leadership support) account for 73–81% of variance in outcomes like retention and productivity (Johannsen and Zak, 2021). Cross-cultural studies, like those conducted in Chinese educational institutions and the banking industry in Bangladesh, further support these connections by demonstrating that peer and supervisor trust mediates the effect of leadership styles on engagement (Tang et al., 2021).

Level of Assessment on Organizational Effectiveness in Terms of Goal Attainment, Efficiency, Employee Satisfaction and Engagement, Communication and Information Flow, Human Resources, Innovation and Adaptability, and Stakeholder Satisfaction

The data from Table 3 computed a grand mean of 3.09 showing that respondents rated the organizations' effectiveness as "high." Every generation has scored highly on the factors related to organizational effectiveness. With an area mean of 3.29 for Strategic Clarity and 3.16 for Goal Attainment, they were primarily convinced by these factors. Efficiency, on the other hand, has the lowest area mean of 2.90.

Table 3. Mean and Qualitative Description of the Respondents' Assessment of Their Organizational Effectiveness in the College of Engineering

Organizational effectiveness components	Mean and Qualitative Description			
	Generation X	Generation Y	Generation Z	Overall Mean
Goal attainment	3.23 (High)	3.05 (High)	3.20 (High)	3.16 (High)
Efficiency	3.07 (High)	2.71 (High)	2.93 (High)	2.90 (High)
Employee satisfaction and engagement	3.17 (High)	2.98 (High)	3.00 (High)	3.05 (High)
Strategic clarity	3.17 (High)	3.36 (High)	3.33 (High)	3.29 (High)
Communication and information flow	3.20 (High)	2.93 (High)	2.80 (High)	2.98 (High)
Human resources	3.17 (High)	3.20 (High)	2.87 (High)	3.08 (High)
Innovation and Adaptability	3.23 (High)	3.20 (High)	3.20 (High)	3.21 (High)
Stakeholder satisfaction	3.07 (High)	3.07 (High)	3.13 (High)	3.09 (High)
Overall mean	3.16 (High)	3.06 (High)	3.06 (High)	3.09 (High)

Important elements that have a direct bearing on an organization's performance are employee satisfaction and engagement. Employees are more imaginative, creative, and driven to go above and beyond expectations when they are happy and fully engaged in their job. Organizations can unleash the potential of their workforce and propel innovation and success by cultivating a good work environment that places a high priority on employee satisfaction and engagement. In the end, making efforts in the well-being of employees may result in greater output, better output levels, and a more cohesive and effective team. According to Anukwuocha et al. (2022), who looked at the workforce

environment and organizational effectiveness, they discovered that social and psychological workplace elements, such as balance between work and personal life and supervisor conduct, descriptions of duties, and information sharing. The performance of an organization is substantially affected by several elements, including job sharing, leave, scheduling conflicts, and working hours.

In terms of goal attainment, the respondents' area means of 3.16 indicates that the respondents believed in the goal attainment of the organization. With this, one gets the sense that the objectives of every single organization describe the level of achievement that they want to achieve in the more distant future. The degree to which they adhere to the organization's objectives stringently is directly proportional to the efficiency of the organization. There is a possibility that organizations would have a better chance of achieving their objectives if they narrowed the list of objectives that they intended to achieve. However, according to Tang et al. (2008), the notion that pursuing many objectives makes it more difficult to achieve one's goals is undoubtedly supported by a significant amount of face validity.

As for the efficiency, findings reveal that all the three generations were assessed as "high" with an area mean of 2.90. The highest mean is Generation Z with a mean of 3.02 while both Generation Y and X having a mean of 2.91. The findings that were given highlight the important connection that exists between the implementation of effective motivating measures and the overall productivity of employees. The happiness, contentment, and satisfaction of an organization's workforce is a significant factor in determining the successfulness and vitality of it. Consequently, in order to achieve high levels of productivity and success inside the organization, it is essential to cultivate a work atmosphere that is both pleasant and stimulating. It is possible for high-performing firms to build a culture that fosters growth, creativity, and success by placing a priority on the health and morale of their workforce. Whether or whether an organization is effective is contingent upon the happiness, contentment, and satisfaction of its employees. In light of this, Pârjoleanu (2020) asserts that any organization that aspires to achieve success need to put into practice an efficient method of motivating. After the adoption of motivational strategies that are tailored to the environment of the organization as well as the types of personnel it employs, the level of happiness that employees have while they are on the job will grow, and they will feel more driven to perform to the greatest possible levels.

Meanwhile, for employee satisfaction and engagement, results indicate that Generation Y has the lowest rating, with a weighted mean of 2.98. A "high" level of engagement and satisfaction is indicated by the fact that Generations X and Z with 3.17 and 3.00, respectively, and an area mean of 3.05. This could mean that organizational performance is determined by employee happiness and engagement. The outcomes are remarkable when employees are happy and driven in their jobs. Contented employees often unleash their creative potential, which sparks a creative explosion at work. They often go above and beyond expectations and voluntarily take on more tasks because of this increased feeling of engagement, proving their dedication to their job and the success of the organization. Organizations may leverage the creativity and commitment of their workforce by cultivating a work environment that puts a premium on employee well-being and engagement. This will eventually lead to development and success. The research conducted by Noercahyo et al. (2021) revealed that although work engagement does not substantially impact organizational performance, it does have a favorable and significant influence on job satisfaction. Additionally, work satisfaction improves and has a big impact on how well an organization performs.

For strategic clarity, the data indicates that the respondents had a "high" level of organizational effectiveness on strategic clarity, with an area mean of 3.29. There was a slight variation in the ratings of the three generations, with Generation Y having the highest mean (3.36), followed by Generation Z (3.33) and Generation X (3.17). It implies that strategic clarity, or the detail with which strategic goals are articulated, and the requisite ability to precisely define, promptly adjust, effectively explain, and appropriately execute will be critical to the organization's success. It highlights how crucial it is to convey strategic objectives clearly and concisely as well as how crucial it is to have the necessary skills to effectively create, modify, express, and carry out the organization's vision, purpose, and goals. This clarity makes sure that everyone in the organization understands and actively pursues a unified objective and

purpose. Strategic clarity directs the organization toward development and accomplishment in a purpose-driven and professional way by promoting alignment and understanding. According to Smith and Thomas (2024), when your institution's strategy is implemented, meaningful, compelling, relevant, clear, and flexible, the organization is heading on the right path in terms of facilitating strategic clarity.

Going to the communication and information flow component, the calculated mean area of 2.98 suggests that the respondents consistently demonstrate a "high" level of evaluation in terms of communication and information flow. Specifically, for Generations XYZ, the averages are 3.20, 2.93 and 2.80 respectively. This implies that effective communication within an organization ensures that workers have a clear understanding of the significance of their position and how their contributions contribute to the success of the organization. Similarly, with the establishment of unambiguous communication channels, organizations may effectively convey their value propositions and accomplishments to customers, so promoting transparency and building confidence. Akarika et al. (2023) asserts that the presence of efficient communication improves organizational performance, among other discoveries. In addition, it is crucial to provide frequent training to staff members to address the obstacles that hinder successful communication, such as inadequate planning, organizational hurdles, semantic barriers, noise interference, poorly articulated communications, deficient listening skills, and lack of trust.

In the component of human resources, the data provides information on the "high" evaluation of the three Generations, with a mean value of 3.08. Generation Y had the highest mean of 3.20, followed by Generation X with 3.17 and Generation Z with 2.87. It suggests that the implementation of human resources development techniques has a favorable correlation with organizational success. This encourages university administrators to implement efficient human resources development strategies that focus on enhancing workers' capabilities and fostering more alignment between organizational performance and the development of human resources. The techniques concerning the growth in human resources, including talent development, training and development, organizational development, and career development, have a positive and substantial influence on organizational performance (Kareem, 2019). Therefore, it can assist university decision-makers in creating efficient human resources development strategies that will enhance staff's abilities and ultimately increase organizational performance.

Moving to innovation and adaptability, an area mean of 3.21 is found, which indicates a "high" perception of innovation and adaptation among Generation XYZ. There are no variations in the means of generation YZ (3.20), and a minimal variation is found in Generation Z (3.23). It suggests that inventive and flexible organizations anticipate changing circumstances in advance and respond to change as it occurs. An organization's capacity to adapt is best measured by how well it performs in a changing environment. Effective organizational leaders must be able to develop their employees so they can adapt to changing conditions. This is a necessary component of successful organizations. To build organizational adaptability, leaders must create a supportive work environment where taking calculated risks and accepting them as normal, considering new ideas, collaborating freely, and rewarding individual adaptation as part of the organization's culture (Boylan & Turner, 2017).

Lastly, for stakeholder satisfaction, it is evident that Generation Z had the highest assessment with a mean of 3.13, while there is no variation in the mean by Generation XY with 3.07. The computed area means of 3.09 indicates a "high" level of satisfaction among stakeholders. This implies that university management should monitor the sense of fulfillment of all its stakeholders, in addition to its clientele, if the stakeholders commit themselves to and provide the required resources for the university's objectives and activities. Universities are seeing more fierce competition. They must adapt and respond flexibly to the evolving challenges and possibilities in tertiary education (Schüller et al., 2014). Consequently, colleges must prioritize the quality of their services and optimize their resources.

Human resources, communication and information flow, goal attainment, efficiency, employee engagement and satisfaction, innovation and adaptability, and stakeholder satisfaction all have a synergistic effect on organizational performance, as evidenced by the high overall mean in organizational effectiveness across these dimensions. Clear objectives eliminate uncertainty and promote resource utilization, which is why empirical studies show that goal clarity and alignment with company vision greatly increase efficiency and employee engagement.

Employees are informed and inspired to contribute to common objectives when there is effective communication and information flow, which serve as vital facilitators for teamwork (Wang and Zhao, 2023). According to research, adaptive firms beat rivals in stakeholder satisfaction by satisfying changing demand, demonstrating the importance of innovation and flexibility in responding to dynamic market conditions. By creating a positive work atmosphere, human resource techniques like talent management and leadership development also increase employee satisfaction and engagement. Psychometric measurements show good reliability across a variety of industries, and factor analyses consistently confirm these dimensions as interconnected factors that jointly predict organizational success. Various results highlight how organizational effectiveness is multifaceted and how crucial it is to integrate various elements for long-term success (Wang and Zhao, 2023).

Relationship Between Organizational Change and Organizational Trust

The data presented in Table 4 demonstrates a significant association between the respondents' evaluation of organizational change and their level of organizational trust. This is apparent from the calculated r-value of 0.69, which much exceeds the required r-value of 0.186 for 18 degrees of freedom at a significance level of 0.05. As a result, the null hypothesis is disproven, confirming a very strong association between how respondents perceive organizational change and their level of trust to the organization.

Table 4. Correlation Coefficient between the Respondents' Assessed Organizational Change and Organizational Trust in the College of Engineering

Compared variables	Compared r-value	Critical r-value	Remarks
Organizational change vs. Organizational trust	0.69 (Very High)	0.186	Very significant

The observed association between how respondents evaluate organizational change and their level of trust in the organization provides useful insights into the internal workings of an organization going through changes. This link highlights the complex connection between employee's perception of organizational changes and their degree of trust in the organization. The positive association indicates that when workers see organizational changes more positively, their trust in the company tends to grow. Effective communication, openness, and engagement in the change process may foster trust among workers. When workers are well-informed and actively involved in decision-making about change, they are more inclined to have confidence in the organization's intentions to prioritize their welfare.

Furthermore, the notable association between organizational change and trust underscores the need to cultivate a nurturing organizational culture during periods of transition. Organizations that give importance to transparent communication, giving employees authority, and adopting a cooperative approach to managing change are more likely to cultivate greater levels of trust among their staff. Moreover, the results indicate that organizational leaders should closely monitor the perception and experience of employees about organizational changes. To effectively manage negative impressions and build trust, it is important to take a proactive approach by addressing concerns, creating chances for input, and implementing support channels.

Gupta and Singla (2017) provided evidence to support the notion that employees should be informed, involved, and integrated into the change process. This approach leads to high motivation and satisfaction among employees, as they are not subjected to forced change but rather actively participate in the process. Therefore, fulfillment at work is a result of the connection between the change in organization and organizational trust. The results of Gupta and Singla (2016) align with the conclusion that organizational change should be implemented within a context of mutual

respect. It also results in the development of a strong emotional connection between the organization and its employees, which subsequently contributes to job satisfaction.

Relationship Between Organizational Change, Trust, and Organizational Effectiveness

The data found in Table 5 and 6 indicates a significant relationship between the respondents' evaluations of organizational change, and effectiveness. This is shown by the estimated r-value of 0.62, which at a significance level of 0.05 substantially exceeds the required r-value of 0.186 for 18 degrees of freedom. As a result, the null hypothesis is disproved, confirming that respondents' assessments of organizational change and effectiveness are significantly correlated. A changing organization's dynamics may be inferred from the noteworthy correlation between respondents' assessments of organizational change and effectiveness. This association highlights the intricate link that exists between employees' views of organizational changes and their level of organizational effectiveness inside the organization.

Table 5. Correlation Coefficient between the Respondents' Assessed Organizational Change and Organizational Effectiveness in the College of Engineering

Compared variables	Compared r-value	Critical r-value	Remarks
Organizational change vs. Organizational effectiveness	0.62 (Very High)	0.186	Very significant

First, the positive association suggests that when workers have a more favorable perception of organizational changes, they are generally more productive inside the company. This shows that engagement in the change process, excellent communication, and transparency may help an organization become efficient. Enriquez (2019) asserts that organizational change occurs continuously. The Social Exchange Theory states that although change happens, organization members make an effort to welcome and accept it, which might lead to the achievement of organizational success in conjunction with education, research, and extension activities. According to Bouckenooghe et al. (2009), when changes were more often than not, the capacity of organizational members to be adaptable and open to change became more crucial. This characterizes the organization's long-term efficacy.

Table 6. Correlation Coefficient between the Respondents' Assessed Organizational Trust and Organizational Effectiveness in the College of Engineering

Compared variables	Compared r-value	Critical r-value	Remarks
Organizational trust vs. Organizational effectiveness	0.54 (Very High)	0.186	Very significant

The considerable relationship between organizational trust and effectiveness is seen in the above table. This is shown by the calculated r-value of 0.54 at a significance level of 0.05, which greatly exceeds the required r-value of 0.186 for 18 degrees of freedom. As a result, the null hypothesis is disproved, confirming a strong relationship between respondents' assessments of organizational change and effectiveness. This suggests that there is a strong correlation between organizational trust and effectiveness. An organization's ability to adapt and build trust is essential to its success and effectiveness. Every employee wants to work in a setting of trust where they are really helping to accomplish goals and objectives.

According to Latifi and Shooshtarian (2014) research, there is a high association between trust characteristics and organizational structure. Additionally, according to Gilley et al. (2009), encouraging progress is being made in hastening change via the activation of hidden social networks and the improvement of their capacity to transcend boundaries across systems, cultures, and organizations. Since change initiatives do not just depend on vertical channels to react to emerging difficulties, leaders who engage these networks significantly increase their organization's ability to handle change.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In summary, the investigation of the relationship between trust and organizational change in a collegiate setting indicates a crucial and intricate interaction. As discussed, trust is both a product and a facilitator of successful change initiatives. Organizational change is more easily embraced when trust is strong, which facilitates transitions and increases organizational efficacy. On the other hand, when trust is low, change initiatives frequently encounter opposition, impeding advancement and possibly destroying the foundation of the campus community. To better understand the precise processes by which confidence is established and preserved during times of transition, more research is required like comparative studies across various colleges within the university. From this output, college deans may create a more positive and productive atmosphere for all parties involved by comprehending these subtleties and using evidence-based techniques to manage change and build trust. Future research could examine how various leadership philosophies affect trust in times of transition and the function of communication techniques. It is suggested also that there must be thorough policies on departmental reorganizations, the introduction of new technologies, curricular reviews, or curricular adjustments, which require a foundation of trust. Staff and faculty members are more inclined to accept and adjust to changes when they believe in the leadership's ability, trust the change's intentions, and feel their concerns are being acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- Akarika, D. C., Iwok, U. A., Afangide, N. G., & Akpan, E. O. (2023). Patterns of communication flow and organizational effectiveness in Local Government Councils in Nigeria. *Sciences*, 11(7), 44-62. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=organizational+effectiveness+in+terms+of+Communication+and+Information+Flow&btnG=
- Al-Abrow, H., Alnoor, A., Ismail, E., Eneizan, B., & Makhamreh, H. Z. (2019b). Psychological contract and organizational misbehavior: Exploring the moderating and mediating effects of organizational health and psychological contract breach in Iraqi oil tanks company. *Cogent Business & Management*, 6(1), 1683123. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2019.1683123>.
- Albrecht, S., Connaughton, S., Foster, K., Furlong, S., & Yeow, C. (2020). Change engagement, change resources and change demands: A model for positive employee orientations to organizational change. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 2854. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.531944>.
- Albrecht, S., Connaughton, S., & Leiter, M. P. (2022). The Influence of Change-Related Organizational and Job Resources on Employee Change Engagement. *Front. Psychol., Sec. Organizational Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.910206>.
- AlbShura, R. D., Rutherford, B. J., Fugett, A., & Lindberg, M. A. (2017). An exploratory study of attachments and posttraumatic stress in combat veterans. *Current Psychology*, 36(1), 110–118. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-015-9390-2>.
- Alnoor, A., Abdullah, H. O., Al-Abrow, H., Wah Khaw, K., Al-Awidi, I. A., Abbas, S., & Omrane, A. (2021). A fuzzy delphi analytic job demands resources model to rank factors influencing open innovation. *Transnational Corporations Review*, 1-15. [10.1080/19186444.2021.1956854](https://doi.org/10.1080/19186444.2021.1956854).
- Appelbaum, S.H., Cameron, A., Ensink, F., Hazarika, J., Attir, R. (2017). Factors that impact the success of an organizational change: a case study analysis. *Industrial and Commercial Training*. 49(5), 213-230. <https://www.sciencegate.app/document/10.1108/ict-02-2017-0006>.

- Anukwuocha, S., Okafor, S., Onyekwere, C. (2022). Workforce environment and organizational effectiveness. SSRN Electronic Journal. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363856054_workforce_environment_and_organizational_effectiveness.
- Ansari, A., & Malik, S. (2017). Ability-based emotional intelligence and knowledge sharing: The moderating role of trust in co-workers. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, 47(2), 211–227.
- Ashkenas, R., Siegal, W., & Spiegel, N. (2013). Mastering organizational complexity: A core competency for 21st century leaders. *Research in Organizational Change and Development*, 21, 29–58.
- Bachmann, R. & Inkpen, C. (2011), “Understanding institutional-based trust building processes in inter-organizational relationships”, *Organization Studies*, 32(2), 281-301, doi:10.1177/0170840610397477.
- Bah, M.O.P., Sun, Z., Hange, U., & Edjoukou, A.J.R. (2024). Effectiveness of Organizational Change through Employee Involvement: Evidence from Telecommunications and Refinery Companies. *Sustainability*, 16(6), 2524. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16062524>
- Beare, E. C., O’Raghallaigh, P., McAvoy, J., & Hayes, J. (2020). Employees’ emotional reactions to digitally enabled work events. *Journal of Decision Systems*, 30(2–3), 235–258. <https://doi.org/10.1080/12460125.2020.1782085>.
- Bhandari, P. (2020). What is quantitative research? Definition, uses & methods. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quantitative-research/>
- Blom, T. (2018). Organizational wellness: Human reaction to change. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 49(1), 10. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajbm.v49i1.2>.
- Bouckenooghe, D., Devos, G., & Van den Broeck, H. (2009). Organizational change questionnaire—climate of change, processes, and readiness: Development of a new instrument. *The Journal of Psychology*, 143(6), 559–599. <https://doi.org/10.3200/JRLP.143.6.559-599>.
- Boylan, S. A., & Turner, K. A. (2017). Developing organ adaptability for complex environment. *Journal of Leadership Education*, 16(2), 183-198.
- Brühl, R., Basel, J. S., & Kury, M. F. (2018). Communication after an integrity-based trust violation: How organizational account giving affects trust. *European Management Journal*, 36, 161–170.
- Enriquez, J. (2019). Organizational effectiveness of Naval State University: Proposed institutional capacity building. *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*, 9(3).
- Errida, A., & Lofti, B. (2021). The determinants of organizational change management success: Literature review and case study. *International Journal of Engineering Business Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/18479790211016273>.
- Fulmer, A. (2018). Multilevel trust: Antecedents and outcomes of trust at different levels. In R. Searle, A. Nienaber, & S. Sitkin (Eds.), *The Routledge companion to trust* (pp. 143–160). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Fulmer, A. & Gelfand, J. (2012). At what level (and in whom) we trust: trust across multiple organizational levels. *Journal of Management*, 38(4), 1167-1230. doi: 10.1177/0149206312439327.
- Gilley, A., McMillan, H. S., & Gilley, J. W. (2009). Organizational change and characteristics of leadership effectiveness. *Journal of leadership & organizational studies*, 16(1), 38-47. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=organizational+change+and+effectiveness&btnG=#d=gs_cit&t=1714479724765&u=%2Fscholar%3Fq%3Dinfo%3AbGZrjG2DyUJ%3Ascholar.google.com%2F%26output%3Dcite%26scirp%3D4%26hl%3Den.
- Gioia, D.A., Corley, K.G. & Hamilton, A.L. (2012). Seeking qualitative rigor in inductive research: notes on the Gioia methodology. *Organizational Research Methods*, 16(1), 15-31, doi: 10.1177/1094428112452151.
- González-Cánovas A, Trillo A, Bretones FD, Fernández-Millán JM. (2024). Trust in leadership and perceptions of justice in fostering employee commitment. *Front Psychol*. 31;15:1359581. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1359581. PMID: 38356764; PMCID: PMC10864523.
- Gopalan, N., Beutell, N.J., & Alstete, J.W. (2023). Can trust in management help? Job satisfaction, healthy lifestyle, and turnover intentions. *International Journal of Organization Theory & Behavior*. 26(3). <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/ijotb-09-2022-0180/full/html>.

- Gupta, S. & Singla, A. (2017). Organizational change and job satisfaction: An analysis of mediating effect of organizational trust. *Indian Journal of Commerce and Management Studies*, 7(3), 07–13. <https://www.ijcms.in/index.php/ijcms/article/view/245>.
- Gustafsson, S., Gillespie, N., Searle, R., Hope Hailey, V. & Dietz, G. (2021). Preserving organizational trust during disruption. *Organization Studies*, 42(9), 1409-1433.
- Helpap, S. (2016). The impact of power distance orientation on recipients' reactions to participatory versus programmatic change communication. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 52(1), 5–34. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021886315617530>.
- Hunt, M., Lara, T. M., & Hughey, A. W. (2009). Establishing and maintaining organizational trust in the 21st century. *Industry and Higher Education*, 23(2), 71-77. <https://doi.org/10.5367/00000000978814658>.
- Hussain, S. T., Lei, S., Akram, T., Haider, M. J., Hussain, S. H., & Ali, M. (2018). Kurt Lewin's change model: A critical review of the role of leadership and employee involvement in organizational change. *Journal of Innovation Knowledge*, 3(3), 123–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2016.07.002>.
- Johannsen, R. & Zak, P.J. (2021). The Neuroscience of Organizational Trust and Business Performance: Findings From United States Working Adults and an Intervention at an Online Retailer. *Front. Psychol., Sec. Organizational Psychology*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.579459>.
- Nazmul Islam, A., Furuoka, F. & Idris, A. (2020). The impact of trust in leadership on organizational transformation. *Global Business and Organizational Excellence A Review of Research & Best Practices*, <https://doi.org/10.1002/joe.22001>.
- Kareem, M. A. (2019). The impact of human resource development on organizational effectiveness: An empirical study. *Management Dynamics in the Knowledge Economy*, 7(1), 29-50. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=organizational+effectiveness+in+terms+of+Human+Resources&btnG=
- Koohang, A., Paliszkievicz, J., & Goluchowski, J. (2017). The impact of leadership on trust, knowledge management, and organizational performance: A research model. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 117(3), 521–537.
- Latifi, M., & Shooshtarian, Z. (2014). The effects of organizational structure on organizational trust and effectiveness. *Polish journal of management studies*, 10(2), 73-84. Latifi, M., & Shooshtarian, Z. (2014). The effects of organizational structure on organizational trust and effectiveness. *Polish journal of management studies*, 10(2), 73-84.
- Lewicki, R.J. & Brinsfield, C. (2012). Measuring trust beliefs and behaviors. In Lyon, F., Möllering, G. and K Saunders, M.N. (Eds), *Handbook of Research Methods on Trust*, Edward Elgar, Cheltenham, Northampton, MA, pp. 29-39.
- Li, A.N. & Tan, H.H. (2013). What happens when you trust your supervisor? Mediators of individual performance in trust relationships. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 34(3), 407-425, doi:10.1002/job.1812.
- Li, M., Wang, Z., Gao, J., & You, X. (2017). Proactive personality and job satisfaction: The mediating effects of self-efficacy and work engagement in teachers. *Current Psychology*, 36(1), 48–55. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-015-9383-1>.
- Macpherson, C. (2017). *The change catalyst: Secrets to successful and sustainable business change*. Chichester, West Sussex, UK: John Wiley & Sons.
- Morgan, G. (2006). *Images of organization*. SAGE Publication, Inc. USA. Morgan, D. E. & Zeffane, R. (2003) Employee involvement, change and trust in management. *International Journal Human Resource Management*, 14, 55–75.
- Noercahyo, U. S., Maarif, M. S., & Sumertajaya, I. M. (2021). The role of employee engagement on job satisfaction and its effect on organizational performance. *Jurnal Aplikasi Manajemen*, 19(2), 296- 309.
- Office of State Personnel. (2015). *Organizational effectiveness model*. Available at: Monster.com.
- Olander, H., Vanhala, M., Hurmelinna-Laukkanen, P., & Blomqvist, K. (2015). HR-related knowledge protection and innovation performance: The moderating effect of trust. *Knowledge and Process Management*, 22(3), 3, 220–3, 233.
- Oreg, S., & Berson, Y. (2011). Leadership and employees 'reactions to change: The role of leaders 'personal attributes and transformational leadership style. *Personnel Psychology*, 64(3), 627–659. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.2011.01221.x>.

- Ozlati, S. (2015). The moderating effect of trust on the relationship between autonomy and knowledge sharing: A national multi-industry survey of knowledge workers. *Knowledge and Process Management*, 22(3), 191–205.
- Pârjoleanu, R. (2020). Work motivation efficiency in the workplace. *Postmodern Openings*, 11(4), 293-309. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=efficiency+in+workplace&btnG=
- Peng, J., Li, M., Wang, Z., & Lin, Y. (2020). Transformational leadership and employees' reactions to organizational change: Evidence from a meta-analysis. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021886320920366>.
- Rahayuningsih, I. (2019). The positive impact of organizational trust: A systematic review. *Journal of Educational Health and Community Psychology*, 8(1). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331705823_The_Positive_Impact_of_Organizational_Trust_a_Systematic_Review.
- Savolainen, T. (2011). Trust management in renewing intellectual capital. In Puusa, A. and Reijonen, H. (Eds), *Intangible Capital as an Organizational Resource*, UNIPress, pp. 117-141.
- Schüller, D., Chlebovský, V., Doubravský, K., & Chalupský, V. (2014). The conceptual scheme for managing university stakeholders' satisfaction. *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*, 62(4), 719-727.
- Scott, D. (1981). The development of four new organizational measures of trust. In D. Ray (Ed.), *The relationship between theory, research, and practice: An assessment of fundamental problems and their possible resolution* (pp. 107-109). Southern Management Association.
- Smith, S. D., & Thomas, T. F. (2024). The effects of strategic alignment and strategic clarity on multidimensional task performance. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 112, 101524. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=organizational+effectiveness+in+terms+of+Strategic+Clarity&btnG=
- Su, T.S., Chen, X., Xiaoyu, C., Yang, C. & Ma, W. (2020a). Consistency at different levels. A meta-analytic examination of organizational trust and performance. *Nankai Business Review International*, 11(4), 537-567.
- Su, W., Lyu, B., Chen, H. & Zhang, Y. (2020b). How does servant leadership influence employees' service innovative behavior? The roles of intrinsic motivation and identification with the leader." *Baltic Journal of Management*, 15(4), 571-586.
- Tang, R., Cai, Y., & Zhang, H. (2021). Paternalistic Leadership and Subordinates' Trust in Supervisors: Mediating Effects of Basic Psychological Needs Satisfaction. *Front. Psychol., Sec. Organizational Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.722620>.
- Tang, Z., Powell, B., Marino, L., Tang, J., & Dickson, P. (2008). The impact of organizational goal setting on the industrial munificence-goal attainment relationship. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 3(3), 107124. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=organizational+effectiveness+in+terms+of+goal+attainment&btnG=
- Tisu, L., Rusu, A., Sulea, C. & Virga, D. (2021). Job resources and strengths use in relation to employee performance: A contextualized view. *Psychological Reports*, 125(3), 1-34.
- Vadil, C. & Castriciones, S. (2023). Organizational effectiveness scale for university setting.
- Vanhala, M., & Dietz, G. (2015). HRM, trust in employer and organizational performance. *Knowledge and Process Management*, 22(4), 270–287.
- Vanhala, M., & Ritala, P. (2016). HRM practices, impersonal trust and organizational innovativeness. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 31(1), 95–109.
- Wang, Y. & Zhao, J. (2023). Theoretical Research on the Evaluation Indicators of Organizational Effectiveness. *Proceedings of the 2022 7th International Conference on Modern Management and Education Technology*. <https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/mmet-22/125977788>.
- Whitaker, S. (2020). *Organizational climate of change dimensions and the effect of gender, race/ethnicity, and years on the job: A quantitative research perspective*. Capella University, Minneapolis, MN, United States.
- Yin, M.A., Korsgaard, A.M., Welpe, I.M., Picot, A. & Wigand, R.T. (2014). The dynamics of shared leadership: building trust and enhancing performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 99(5), 771-783, doi: 10.1037/a0036474.